

APPLICATION CONSTRUCTION AS A TYPE OF SYNTACTIC COMMUNICATION

Azizova Zarinakhan Alikhanovna

Teacher of the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10450018>

Annotation . In the article, the nlova construction is studied as one of the structural types of a complex syntactic whole, in which its structural structure and semantic features, and the grammatical expression of the components that make them up, as well as the syntactic relations between the components involved in the organization of syntactic units, are analyzed by means of examples taken from the German language and related conclusions are reached.

Keywords. Application event, application construction, complex syntactic entity, application element, syntactic connection, structural type, parallel connection, communicative center

A large number of articles, monographs, candidate and doctoral theses were written, which were the object of special scientific research in many languages, as a syntactic-stylistic phenomenon of the application construction [2; p. 65]. In the framework of this scientific research, the attachment construction is interpreted as one of the structural groups of a complex syntactic whole. A complex syntactic entity is, in turn, a structural representation of the text.

Therefore, the attachment construction is one of the structural types of a complex syntactic whole, and in modern linguistics, a complex syntactic whole is becoming the object of many scientific researches as a syntactic-stylistic phenomenon, and we are witnessing the emergence of new forms of it. In order to prove our point, we consider it appropriate to cite the following terminological concepts formalized in Russian regarding complex syntactic integrity : «Slojnoe sintaxischeskoe tseloe», «slojnye sintaxischeskoe kompleksy», «slojnoe sintaxischeskoe edinstvo», «prozaicheskaya strofa», «krupnyy tekst», «bolshoe sintaxischeskoe tseloe». ", "obshirny syntactical complex" [2; p. 71].

Thus, regardless of how such diverse terminological concepts applied to a complex syntactic whole are called, they have a single linguistic essence and serve only for this syntactic stylistic phenomenon. However, when interpreting the linguistic essence of a complex syntactic whole, it is necessary to take into account their structural types. A complex syntactic unit is such a form of syntactic units existing in the language that several simple and compound sentences that make up its component are grammatically independent and are related to each other in terms of common content. In other words, in a complex syntactic whole, there is a common meaningful relationship between several independent simple or compound sentences. This meaningful relationship emerges on the basis of a certain object or event. In this case, independent sentences are related to each other through actions and situations, and one defines, completes and explains the meaning of the other. In some cases, their specific meaning can be generalized.

The structural structure and semantic features of a complex syntactic whole depend on the grammatical expression of the components that make them up. In such cases, it is necessary to determine the type and nature of the syntactic relations between the components involved in the organization of syntactic units, because the syntactic relations between them play an important role in the division of a complex syntactic whole into structural types. For example, G. Ya. Solganik, in his research work entitled "Syntax Semantics", when dividing a complex syntactic entity into structural types, based on the nature of the syntactic relations between its constituent components, finds it necessary to divide a complex syntactic entity into structural types as follows: 1) complex syntactic entities based on string relations syntactic integrity (in it: prosaicheskaya strofa s tsepnoy svyazyu); 2) a complex syntactic whole based on parallel connections (in it: prosaicheskaya strofa s parallelnymi svyazami); 3) a complex syntactic entity based on application relations (in it: prosaicheskaya struktura s prisoedinennoy svyazyu) [1 ; 6 7 -p.].

In this monographic work, the author separately explains the characteristics of each structural type of complex syntactic whole.

G. Ya. In this monograph, Solganik gives some ideas about the structural type of complex syntactic whole based on the structural group based on linear and parallel relations. A complex syntactic entity based on an application structure has two names in the monographic work: an application construction or a complex syntactic entity based on an application relationship [1; pp. 21-23].

This complex syntactic entity based on adjunctive connections differs from complex syntactic entities based on series and parallel connections by its structural formation. This difference is expressed primarily by the fact that the additional elements joining the main expression have intonation completeness. Putting a punctuation mark "point" between the components of such a complex syntactic whole, firstly, it shows the grammatical independence of the main expression in the complex syntactic whole, and secondly, it shows that the additional elements joining it are not structurally and intonationally independent components. Additional elements give additional meaning to the components to which they depend, concretize, complete, expand, enrich and explain its content. App elements can only come in the app element function within the app construct. Such properties specific to application elements can also be seen in the context instance . For example, a decontextualized sentence retains grammatical independence, but loses the conceptual integrity associated with other sentences in the context. If adjunctive elements are separated from the structure of an adjunct construction, then the adjunctive construction loses its linguistic essence of being an adjunct construction.

An application construction, or in other words, a complex syntactic whole based on application relations, serves to maintain and create intellectual completeness in the process of connected speech, similar to other structural types. A group of sentences that are conceptually and syntactically interrelated is called a complex syntactic entity, and its structural type based on attachment relations is called an attachment construction.

The attached construction consists of two parts according to its structural structure: the main part and attached elements (the number of attached elements can be more than one). The content of additional elements is more important both syntactically and semantically, because they always receive logical emphasis.

Now we will pay attention to the strengthening of the additional meaning characteristics expressed by the additional elements in relation to the main expression with the help of the additional elements of various forms.

Fr a nzösische Wörter oder Satze hatte er nicht gedacht. Kurz vor dem Sprung nicht und auch vorher nicht [Herbert Otto 1972: 258].

This on the ground app construction each other _ with mutually substantive in touch has been of words from the total organize found the only one from paragraph consists of The events described in this application are directly related to family life. In order to show the important aspects of the described event for the family, for saving the family , the writer uses some syntactic figures. In the function of such syntactic figures, there are additional elements that have a continuous character. These adjuncts are expressed using prepositions requiring genitive agreement, structurally simple adjuncts. However, this Although the attached elements are considered simple structural attached elements, one differs from the other in its own characteristics.

Selbst die Mutter geht nicht mehr gern in den Wald. Nur um die Mittagszeit wagt sie sich bis an die Lichtung und holt Gras für die Ziege. Auch Beeren. Und Pilze. [Bruns Marianne 1972: 96].

In the above example, the additional meanings of the additional element, such as demarcation, subtraction, emphasis, addition, are added to the additional meanings of the additional elements, and they concretize, fill in, explain and develop the events taking place in the main expression. An action, state or character in the application structure components occurs sequentially at the same time.

In the scientific research dedicated to the study of the properties characteristic of additional elements, it is emphasized that the logical emphasis is not on the additional elements, but on the nuclei in the composition of their additional element compounds. Since the auxiliary elements belong to the group of auxiliary nouns, there are many concepts that they do not have their own lexical meaning, they are considered invariable, non-variable, non-descriptive words, because they do not receive a logical accent. However, situations that occur within the text, contextual environments, and concrete examples confirm that the applied elements have a logical emphasis.

So, in the example, it is emphasized that the words and phrases used in the function of the auxiliary element, the auxiliary elements not only have a logical emphasis in certain contextual environments, but also that they are used in the function of communicative units. Such features characteristic of applied elements, firstly, lead to concretization and expansion of the concepts of applied elements, and secondly , in order to reveal such characteristics characteristic of them, it is necessary to get acquainted with the creative activities of many writings and to study them.

The adjunctive elements in these adjunctive constructions are expressed using words or adjunctive phrases. The words that appear in the function of the auxiliary element in the example are repeated variants of the word *ja* that appears in the main expression , that is, the auxiliary elements are formed based on the principle of repetition. Although the additional elements created on the basis of the repeating principle do not convey any new message, they are repeated in order to show its importance and attract the reader's attention. He usually repeats it in order to emphasize the semantically and stylistically more important part of the text.

So, relying on the above opinions, it should be emphasized here that the presuppositional, denotative, connotative, explicit and implicit factors involved in the realization of the pragmatic function of the language are not the only factors, but they should be supplemented and enriched by future scientific research. we hope it is possible.

References:

- 1.Solganik G.Ya. Syntax stylistics (Slojnoe syntaxicheskoe tseloe). Uchebnoe posobie. M., 1991, - 182 p. 67.
- 2.Tursunov B.T., Oblakulova S.Kh. The bibliographic index po voprosam slojnogo syntaxischeskogo tselogo, prisoedineniya, partsellirovaniya. - Samarkand: SamGU. 1982. -72 p.
- 3.Tursunov B.T. Prisoedinenie kak osoby type syntaxischeskoy svyazi. Diss... d-ra filol. science - St. Petersburg, 1993. - 465 p.
- 4.Bruns Marianne. Die Lichtung. Mitteldeutscher Verlag Halle (Saale) 1972.460
- 5.Herbert Otto. Zum Beispiel Josef.Aufbauverlag Berlin und Weimar, 1972, 285 S.
- 6.Reinowski Werner Zwei Brüder. Mitteldeutscher Verlag Halle (Saale), 1972, 562 S.